

A SIMPLE WATER SAMPLES STORAGE TEST FOR WATER ISOTOPE ANALYSIS

M. NIGRO,

Earth Science Department, University of Pisa, Pisa, Italy

E-mail address: matteo.nigro@phd.unipi.it.

P. VREČA, K. ŽAGAR

Department of Environmental Sciences, Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Abstract:

Preventing water samples evaporation is crucial for the quality of water stable isotopes analysis. Storing samples not in glass bottles, and repetitive opening of laboratory reference materials (LRM) sub-sample for daily operation, may impact the quality of analysis results. Here storing in HDPE bottles with no double cap and repetitive analysis of an LRM sub-sample replica were tested. Only this latter showed some evidence of evaporation during the observation period.

1. INTRODUCTION

In every experimental discipline, reliable data are the foundation of quality research. For water stable isotopes (i.e. ^1H , ^2H , ^{16}O , ^{17}O , ^{18}O), this primarily implies preventing evaporation and consequent isotopic enrichment of the samples or the laboratory reference materials (LRM) sub-sample [1] used in the laboratory daily operation. Tight-seal glass bottles constitute the optimal sampling and conservation conditions [1–3], while plastic bottles appear to cause isotopic drifts over long storage periods due to water permeation through the plastic material [1]. However, glass bottles are not always used for sampling, and delays in the analysis may occur. At the same time, the repetitive opening of the LRM sub-sample may cause a drift in its isotopic composition.

The present work aimed to provide quantitative information on the effects of not in glass storing and multi-day usage of LRM sub-sample over the analysis of water stable isotopes.

2. METHODS

Twenty-one Milli-Q water samples were collected from the same starting batch, stored in HDPE bottles with single cap and filled to the top without air bubbles inside. One aliquot was poured into a 60 ml bottle, while the other 20 were collected in 15 ml bottles. The samples were stored for about 80 days at room temperature and humidity. Both temperature and relative humidity were recorded during the testing period. The isotopic composition of oxygen ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$ expressed in per mil, ‰) and hydrogen ($\delta^2\text{H}$ expressed in per mil, ‰) were determined using a water- CO_2 and water- H_2 (platinum – Pt) equilibration technique (with automated H_2 - H_2O and CO_2 - H_2O equilibrators HDOeq48) on a dual inlet isotope ratio mass spectrometer (IRMS) Finnigan MAT DELTA plus at the Jožef Stefan Institute. All measurements were performed together with LRM calibrated periodically against primary IAEA calibration standards to VSMOW/SLAP scale. The results were normalized to VSMOW/SLAP using LIMS (Laboratory Information Management System for Light Stable Isotopes) program.

The 60 ml sample was measured repeatedly during the observation period, extracting every time the necessary 3 ml water volume, to mimic an LRM sub-sample multi-days usage. Each 15 ml sample was analyzed once. Before every analysis, the bottles weights were recorded. The weighting of each of the 15 ml bottles was interrupted after their analysis.

The data evaluation was conducted under the two following assumptions: (i) all samples had the same starting $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ values and (ii) all 15 ml bottles were identical and tightly closed after the filling. Sample evaporation (with its consequent weight loss and isotopic enrichment

in heavy isotopes) is considered the only possible consequence of not being in glass storing condition and multi-day usage of LRM sub-sample.

3. RESULTS

The average storing temperature and humidity were about 24 °C and 50% respectively, during the experiment. No significant change in any bottle weights was detected. The $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ results fulfilled the Westgard rules [4, 5] for quality control in all cases except $\delta^2\text{H}$ data of the multiple 15 ml bottles for one value higher than $+3\sigma$ from the mean. If such outlier is ignored, then Westgard rules are fulfilled also for $\delta^2\text{H}$ data of the multiple 15 ml bottles. For the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ measurements of the single 60 ml bottle the Mann-Kendall trend testing [6] resulted in a p-value of 0.14. Two measurements of this latter dataset, were respectively more than $+2\sigma$ and almost more than $+3\sigma$ from the mean, while all other measurements were never more than $\pm 1\sigma$ from the mean. Hence, the Mann-Kendall testing was repeated removing the two outliers and the p-value was then 0.02 (lower than the standard 0.05 limit). In both cases the coefficient of the linear regression resulted in a positive value. All other data show no significant variations.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Testing of the not in glass storing and multi-day usage of LRM sub-sample effects for water stable isotopes were tested. The only significant and positive trend was detected in the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values of the sample mimicking the LRM sub-sample, suggesting evaporation over the study period due to repeated opening of the bottle. The 15 ml HDPE bottle with no double cap samples did not show significant variation over the study period.

Acknowledgment: The activities for this investigation were supported by the Slovenian Research Agency ARRS (grant no. P1-0143), Cost Action 19120 Watson STSM (E-COST-GRANT-CA19120-019492e2) and Erasmus+. We thank S. Žigon for help with isotope analyses.

REFERENCES

- [1] GRÖNING, M., TEL Technical Note No. 03. Stable Isotope Internal Laboratory Water Standards: Preparation, Calibration and Storage, Terrestrial Environment Laboratory, International Atomic Energy Agency, Vienna, Austria (2018) p. 12.
- [2] CLARK, I.D., FRITZ, P., Environmental Isotopes in Hydrogeology, CRC Press/Lewis Publishers, Boca Raton, FL (1997) 328 pp.
- [3] KENDALL, C., CALDWELL, E.A., “Fundamentals of Isotope Geochemistry”, Isotope Tracers in Catchment Hydrology, Elsevier (1998) 51–86.
- [4] DUNN, P., CARTER, J., Good Practice Guide for Isotope Ratio Mass Spectrometry. Second Edition, <https://www.forensic-isotopes.org/assets/FIRMS%20Good%20Practice%20Guide%20Second%20Edition.pdf>.
- [5] THOMPSON, M., WOOD, R., Harmonized guidelines for internal quality control in analytical chemistry laboratories (Technical Report), Pure and Applied Chemistry **67** 4 (1995) 649.
- [6] KENDALL, M.G., Rank Correlation Methods, 4th ed., Griffin, London (1970) 202 pp.